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Effects of Institutional Financial Services on the Livelihood of Rice Farmers in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the effects of institutional financial services on the livelihood of rice farmers in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was used to select 374 respondents from three Local Government Areas across the state's agricultural zones. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed with descriptive and inferential statistics, including the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. Results showed that 68.2% of respondents were male, 71.9% were within the active age range (21–40 years), and 93.3% were married, with an average farming experience of 13.8 years. The major financial institutions accessible to farmers were cooperative societies (93.3%), NGOs (92.7%), and commercial banks (89.6%). The most utilized financial services included banking transactions (96.3%), credit and loan facilities (80.0%), and insurance (70.3%). However, 70.1% of the households had low to medium livelihood status, indicating limited welfare improvement despite access to financial services. The correlation analysis ($r = 0.008$; $p = 0.879$) revealed no significant relationship between the utilization of formal financial services and household livelihood status. Key constraints identified included untimely disbursement of credit, delayed credit information, inadequate collateral, high input costs, and poor road infrastructure. The study concludes that while formal financial institutions are available and moderately utilized, their impact on livelihoods remains limited due to structural, institutional, and socioeconomic barriers. Strengthening credit delivery systems, promoting financial literacy, and improving rural infrastructure are therefore essential for enhancing agricultural productivity and rural welfare in Nasarawa State.

Keywords: Effects, institutional, financial services, livelihood, rice farmers

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains the cornerstone of Nigeria's economy and the principal source of livelihood for most of its population. According to Belay et al. (2023), agricultural production forms the foundation of livelihoods in developing countries. Globally, about 500 million smallholder farming households representing approximately 2.5 billion people depend on agriculture for their survival (Onyiriuba et al., 2020).

Livelihood encompasses the activities, assets, and access that jointly determine an individual or household's ability to secure food, water, shelter, and clothing (Mphande, 2016). In Nigeria, about 90% of rural households engage in agricultural activities for sustenance and income generation (Moahid & Maharjan, 2020; Osabohien et al., 2020). Understanding rural livelihood in this context is crucial, as it guides institutional financial services in designing targeted products such as microloans, seasonal credit, and agricultural insurance to meet the specific needs of farmers (FAO, 2023; UNDP, 2023).

Institutional financial services refer to the range of financial products and support systems such as credit, savings, insurance, and advisory services provided by formal financial institutions to improve the economic wellbeing of individuals (Onyekwere & Nworgu, 2020). Access to these services is essential for improving agricultural productivity, reducing vulnerability, and enhancing rural livelihoods. Livelihood improvement is often measured in terms of poverty reduction, income growth, and access to food, health, and education (Alao et al., 2020; Gautam & Jha, 2022).

Rice (*Oryza sativa*), often referred to as the “staple of staples,” plays an indispensable role in Nigeria’s food security and rural economy. It serves as both a dietary mainstay and a major source of income for millions of smallholder farmers and processors (Ademiluyi et al., 2021; Obianefo et al., 2023). Nigeria is the largest producer and consumer of rice in West Africa (Ali et al., 2020), yet domestic production remains insufficient to meet national demand. Current production of about 3.3 million metric tonnes falls short of the 5.2 million metric tonnes required annually (Ali et al., 2020), leading to heavy dependence on imports and consequent foreign exchange losses estimated at \$17.26 million between 2000 and 2021 (FAO, 2022). This production deficit underscores the urgent need to address key constraints limiting rice output, among which inadequate access to institutional financial services remains prominent. Financial institutions including commercial banks, microfinance banks, cooperative societies, and development banks play a vital role in supporting agricultural enterprises by providing credit, insurance, savings, and financial literacy programmes (Jima & Makoni, 2023; Koroma, 2016). These services enable farmers to invest in productivity-enhancing technologies, adopt improved practices, and improve household welfare (Guei & Choga, 2022). Nasarawa State, located in Nigeria’s North Central region the country’s food basket has enormous potential for rice production due to its fertile land and proximity to the Federal Capital Territory. The presence of financial institutions and agricultural programmes provides an enabling environment for evaluating how access to formal financial services influences farmers’ livelihoods. Understanding this relationship is therefore essential for designing policies that enhance financial inclusion, increase rice productivity, and improve rural welfare.

Problem Statement

Despite its importance, rice production in Nigeria has not kept pace with rising population and consumption demand. This persistent shortfall contributes to increased import dependence, loss of foreign exchange, and reduced farmer income. Government and donor-funded programmes such as the Anchor Borrowers’ Programme (CBN, 2016), Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (Ojo & Oluwaseun, 2015), and Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CBN, 2018) were established to promote agricultural financing. However, their impact on rice farmers’ productivity and livelihood outcomes have been limited (Ayinde et al., 2018; Azubugwu & Osuafor, 2019). Many smallholder farmers remain trapped in poverty due to inadequate access to formal financial services, poor infrastructure, low literacy levels, and weak institutional support (Koroma, 2016). Consequently, they rely on informal credit sources that often charge high interest rates and offer minimal financial security. These constraints hinder farmers from expanding production, adopting improved technologies, or coping with market and climate shocks. Previous studies (Nolon & Rael, 2021; Yusuf et al., 2022; Dare et al., 2017; Georgina et al., 2020) have shown that access to institutional finance significantly enhances farmers’ income and welfare, but evidence remains limited for Nasarawa State. Given the state’s strategic role in national rice production, it is imperative to assess how institutional financial services influence the livelihood of rice farmers, including their income, food security, and overall wellbeing. This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by empirically examining the effects of institutional financial services on the livelihood of rice farmers in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The broad objective of the study is to assess the effects of institutional financial services on the livelihood of rice farmers in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: describe the socio-economic characteristics of rice farmers in the study area; identify the types of institutional financial services available to rice farmers; assess the level of utilization of institutional financial services by rice farmers; examine the household livelihood status of rice farmers; and determine the relationship between utilization of institutional financial services and the livelihood status of rice farmers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Nasarawa State is located in the North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria and serves as a geographical link between several neighboring states. It shares boundaries with Kaduna State to the north, the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja) to the west, Kogi and Benue States to the south, and Taraba and Plateau States to the east. The State covers a total land area of approximately 27,117 km², with an estimated population of about 2.89 million people as of 2022 (Wikipedia, 2022). Geographically, it lies between latitudes 7°–9° N and longitudes 8°–32° E, placing it within the tropical climatic zone characterized by alternating wet and dry seasons. Average monthly temperatures range from 25 °C in October to about 36 °C in March, while annual rainfall varies between 1,370 mm and 1,450 mm. Administratively, the State is divided into three agricultural zones; Southern, Central, and Western based on ecological and socio-economic similarities. The major crops cultivated include rice, maize, yam, groundnut, sesame, millet, sorghum, cowpea, cassava, melon, sweet potato, okra, and tree crops such as mango, cashew, and shea butter. The major ethnic groups are Eggon, Afo, Egbira, Mada, Nyankpa, Gwandara, Rindre, and Hausa (Ademiluyi et al., 2021; Salau et al., 2013).

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The study targeted all rice farmers in Nasarawa State who had accessed formal financial services. A multistage sampling technique was employed to select the respondents. In the first stage, one Local Government Area (LGA) was purposively selected from each of the three agricultural zones of the State based on the concentration of registered rice farmers. The selected LGAs were Karu (Western Zone), Akwanga (Central Zone), and Awe (Southern Zone). In the second stage, a total of 374 respondents were randomly selected from a population of 5,670 registered rice farmers across the three selected LGAs. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula at a 5% margin of error, and Bourley's proportional allocation formula was used to proportionally distribute the sample size among the LGAs. The Rice Farmers Association of Nigeria (RIFAN) provided the list of registered farmers, and its officials assisted as trained enumerators during data collection.

Data Collection

Primary data were used for the study. These were collected using a well-structured questionnaire administered to the selected rice farmers. The instrument was designed to elicit information relevant to the study objectives, including socio-economic characteristics, types and extent of access to financial services, utilization levels, and livelihood outcomes. Prior to the main survey, enumerators were trained to ensure proper understanding of the questions and accuracy in data recording.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data obtained were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and means were employed to analyze the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, and the types of formal financial services accessed by the respondents. To examine the level of utilization of formal financial services, utilization was categorized into three levels: Low utilization (1–39%), Moderate utilization (40–69%), High utilization (70% and above). Percentages were computed to determine the distribution of respondents across these categories. The household livelihood status of the respondents, was analyzed using a livelihood scale adapted from Yashodhara and Narasimha (2015). The instrument contained 50 items measured along a four-point continuum: Highly Satisfied (4), Satisfied (3), Less Satisfied (2), and Not Satisfied (1). For negatively worded items, the scoring was reversed. The total livelihood status score of a respondent was obtained by summing the scores across all items, yielding a possible range between 50 and 200. Scores greater than 163 indicated a high livelihood status, scores between 142 and 163 represented a medium level, while scores below 142 signified a low livelihood status. The decision rule was adopted from Fredricks et al. (2017). The relationship between the utilization of formal financial services and household livelihood status, was examined using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Model Specification

Let:

X = Utilization of formal financial services (e.g., access to credit, savings, insurance, and other financial products)

Y = Household livelihood status (measured through income, asset ownership, food security, and general welfare indicators)

The correlation coefficient r measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the two variables. It is defined as:

$$r = \frac{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum(X_i - \bar{X})^2 \sum(Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}}$$

The statistical significance of r was tested using the Student's t-test:

$$t = \frac{\sqrt{n-2}r}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

Where:

n = total number of paired observations

r = sample Pearson correlation coefficient

r^2 = coefficient of determination, representing the proportion of variance in one variable explained by the other

t = computed test statistic used to test the null hypothesis $H_0: \rho=0$

$df=n-2$ = degrees of freedom.

The constraints to effective utilization of formal financial services, was analyzed using a five-point Likert-type scale. Respondents were asked to indicate the severity of each constraint using the following scale: Very Serious Constraint (VSC) = 5, Serious Constraint (SC) = 4, No Effect Constraint (NEC) = 3, Not Very Serious Constraint (NVSC) = 2, Not Serious Constraint (NSC) = 1. Weighted means were computed to determine the relative seriousness of each constraint using the formula:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum F_i (A_i)}{5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1}$$

Where:

F_i = frequency of respondents selecting a particular rating

A_i = numerical value assigned to each rating

N = total number of respondents

A weighted mean ≥ 3.0 indicated a serious constraint, whereas a weighted mean < 3.0 implied a less serious or non-significant constraint. This method allowed for an objective ranking of the challenges limiting farmers' access to and utilization of formal financial services.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic Characteristics of Respondents in the Study Area

The socio-economic profile of rice farmers in Wase Local Government Area revealed that the majority (68.2%) were male, suggesting that men dominate rice production due to cultural norms and land tenure systems that favour male land ownership and, consequently, better access to credit. Most farmers (71.9%) were within the active age range of 21–40 years, with a mean age of 31 years, indicating a productive and economically active population capable of adopting innovations and participating in formal financial systems.

A large proportion (93.3%) of the respondents were married, which suggests social and household stability, characteristics that enhance creditworthiness. Educational attainment was generally high, with all respondents having at least primary education, 44.7% had secondary, and 34.0% tertiary education.

This relatively high literacy level implies improved ability to understand loan procedures and engage effectively with financial institutions.

The majority (55.6%) had small household sizes (1–5 persons), while the average household size was 4 persons, implying moderate family labour and consumption levels. Most respondents (73.0%) cultivated between 1–3 hectares, with an average of 2.9 hectares, showing that rice production is largely small-scale. The predominance of family-owned farmlands (63.6%) highlights limited access to formal land titles, a key constraint to using land as collateral for loans.

The average farming experience was 13.8 years, showing substantial technical knowledge and skill, which may improve access to financial support. Most respondents (62.8%) were members of cooperative societies, which serve as important channels for accessing credit and financial literacy training. In addition, 66.6% had contact with agricultural extension agents, an important factor that enhances awareness of formal financial opportunities and best farming practices.

Income distribution revealed that most farmers (56.4%) earned less than ₦1,000,000 annually, with an average income of ₦954,881.02, indicating modest earning levels and financial vulnerability among smallholders. Overall, the findings suggest that socio-economic factors such as education, experience, cooperative membership, and extension contact positively influence farmers' ability to access and utilize formal financial services, while land tenure and low income remain major constraints.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents (n=374)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Sex			
Male	255	68.2	
Female	119	31.8	
Age (years)			
21-30	135	36.1	31 years
31-40	134	35.8	
41-50	38	10.2	
51 and above	67	17.9	
Marital status			
Single	25	6.7	
Married	349	93.3	
Household size (Number of persons)			
1-5	208	55.6	4
6-10	157	42.0	
11-15	9	2.4	
Level of education			
Primary education	80	21.3	
Secondary education	167	44.7	
Tertiary education	127	34.0	
Method of land acquisition			
Inherited farm land	28	7.5	
Farm freely on family farm land	238	63.6	
Purchased land	75	20.1	
Rented land	33	8.8	
Farm size (hectares)			
1-3	273	73.0	2.9
4-6	92	24.6	
7-9	9	2.4	
Rice farming experience (years)			
1-10	120	32.1	13.8
11-20	196	52.4	

21-30	58	15.5	
Cooperative society membership			
Yes	235	62.8	
No	139	37.2	
Years of cooperative membership (years)			
Non-members	139	37.2	3.2
1-5	147	39.3	
6-10	61	16.3	
11-15	15	4.0	
16-20	12	3.2	
Access to extension services			
Yes	249	66.6	
No	125	33.4	
Frequency of extension contact			
1-3			
4-6	125	33.4	2
7-9	160	42.8	
>9	62	16.6	
	27	7.2	
Estimated rice annual income (₦)			
1,000-1,000,000	211	56.4	954, 881 .02
1,001,000-2,000,000	33	8.8	
2,001,000-3,000,000	7	1.9	
Above 3,000,000	123	32.9	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Types of Formal Financial Institutions Available in the Study Area

Table 2 presents the types of formal financial institutions that were both available and accessible in the study area. Findings revealed that cooperative societies (93.3%), non-governmental organizations (92.7%), and commercial banks (89.6%) were the most accessible formal financial institutions to rice farmers in the study area, followed by the Bank of Agriculture (56.1%) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (53.7%). This indicates a relatively high level of availability and accessibility of financial services. Cooperative societies play a major role in providing low-interest loans, savings, and input procurement services tailored to smallholder farmers' needs. NGOs and commercial banks complement these efforts by offering credit facilities, capacity building, and financial literacy programs. Furthermore, specialized institutions like the Bank of Agriculture and the CBN enhance agricultural financing through government-backed schemes such as the Anchor Borrowers' Programme. These findings are consistent with those of Sakiru (2013), Victor et al. (2020), and Mbutor et al. (2013), who reported that cooperative societies, commercial banks, and microfinance institutions were the most commonly accessed sources of agricultural finance among farmers.

Table 2: Types of Formal Financial Institution Available in the Study Area

Formal financial institution	*Frequency	Percentage (%)
Cooperative Society	349	93.3
Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)	347	92.7
Commercial bank	335	89.6
Bank of Agriculture (BOA)	210	56.1
Central Bank	201	53.7
Farmers' Association	169	45.2
Micro finance Bank	86	23.0
Community Bank	30	8.3

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Multiple responses allowed

Level of Utilization of Formal Financial Service by Respondents in the Study Area

Findings in Table 3 revealed a high level of utilization of formal financial services among rice farmers in the study area. The most commonly used services were banking transactions (96.3%), loan and credit services (80.0%), insurance (70.3%), wealth management (66.6%), and project planning. Banking services were the most utilized, providing farmers with access to savings, payments, and transfers that promote financial security and planning. Loan and credit services enabled investment in improved inputs and technologies but were moderately utilized due to constraints such as high interest rates and collateral requirements. Insurance services helped reduce vulnerability to risks such as crop failure and climate shocks, though uptake remained modest due to limited awareness and trust issues.

Wealth management services contributed to improved household welfare by enhancing financial literacy, budgeting, and access to advisory support, consistent with Akinwunmi et al. (2020), who reported that 67.8% of farmers accessed wealth management services in Nigeria. Project planning services facilitated record-keeping and loan documentation, thereby strengthening access to future credit and investment planning. This aligns with Yusuf and Shehu (2022), who emphasized that integrating project planning into financial literacy programs enhances the sustainability of rural agricultural finance. Overall, these findings indicate that formal financial services significantly contribute to improving farmers' productivity, resilience, and livelihood outcomes in Nasarawa State, corroborating Ilavbarhe (2007), who found similar trends among farmers in Edo State.

Table 3: Level of Utilisation of Formal Finance Service by Respondents in the Study Area

Utilization of Formal Finance Service	Frequency	Percentage
Banking transactions	364	96.3
Loan/credit	300	80.0
Insurance service	264	70.3
Wealth management	249	66.6
Project planning	155	41.4
Training on product marketing	149	39.8
Storage of valuables	118	31.6

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Decision rule: Any score between 1-39% = low utilisation, 40-69% = moderate utilisation, and 70% and above = high utilisation.

Household Livelihood Status of the Respondents in the Study Area

The results presented in Table 4 show that 43.6% of the respondents had a low household livelihood status, 26.5% were at a medium level, and only 29.9% had a high household livelihood status. This implies that the majority (70.1%) of the rice-farming households in the study area did not attain the higher livelihood status threshold, indicating widespread vulnerability and limited well-being among the farming population. Household livelihood status serves as a comprehensive measure that encompasses income level, food security, education, access to basic services, and resilience to economic or environmental shocks. The large proportion of households with low livelihood status suggests prevalent rural poverty, food insecurity, and limited access to essential services such as education, healthcare, and clean water. Consequently, these households remain more susceptible to economic instability, climate-related risks (such as floods and droughts), and market price fluctuations, which can further deepen poverty levels. Furthermore, the low livelihood status observed among rice farmers may be attributed to limited access to productive resources, including quality seeds, fertilizers, irrigation facilities, and mechanized tools. Such constraints hinder farmers' ability to increase production, adopt modern technologies, and improve yields. Additionally, inadequate investment in post-harvest management and marketing further reduces their profitability and livelihood outcomes. This finding contrasts with the results of Yashodhara and Narasimha (2015), whose livelihood status assessment among 30 farmers in Chickballapur revealed that 70.0% of the respondents had a medium to high level of livelihood status, suggesting better welfare conditions compared to the current study area.

Table 4: Household Livelihood Status in the Study Area (n=374)

Household Livelihood Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Higher livelihood score level	112	29.9
Medium livelihood score level	99	26.5
Lower livelihood levels	163	43.6

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Note: Higher score (> 163) on this scale indicated that the respondent has higher level of livelihood status. Medium level score ranges between 142 and 163 and while score less than 142 indicated lower livelihood levels.

Relationship between Utilization of Formal Financial Services of Respondents and Household Livelihood Status

The analysis of the relationship between the utilization of formal financial services and household livelihood status as presented in Table 5 revealed a very weak positive correlation ($r = 0.008$) that was not statistically significant ($p = 0.879$). This indicates that the use of formal financial services had no meaningful linear influence on the livelihood status of rice-farming households in the study area. The mean utilization score of 114.32 (SD = 10.733) suggests a moderately high engagement with formal financial institutions but with some variability among respondents. The absence of a significant relationship implies that factors such as education, employment, and access to informal financial systems likely play stronger roles in shaping household welfare. It is also possible that available financial services are not being effectively utilized for productive purposes for example, using credit for consumption instead of investment. Additionally, the impact of financial inclusion may require a longer period to manifest, which a cross-sectional study cannot fully capture. Limited financial literacy among farmers may further constrain effective utilization. This result is consistent with the findings of Victor et al. (2015), who reported a weak (25%) correlation between financial service usage and household livelihood status, suggesting that access alone is insufficient to improve welfare without proper utilization.

Table 5: Relationship between Utilisation of Formal Financial Services and Household Livelihood Status of the Respondents in the Study Area

Variables		Household livelihood status	Level of utilisation of formal financial services
Household livelihood status	Pearson Correlation	1	.008
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.879
	N	374	374
Level of utilisation of formal financial services	Pearson Correlation	.008	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.879	
	N	374	374
Standard deviation = 10.733			
Mean = 114.32			

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Constraints to Effective Utilization of Formal Financial Services by the Respondents

The result presented in Table 6 identified several major constraints affecting the effective utilization of formal financial services among rice farmers in the study area. The key challenges included untimely credit disbursement ($\bar{x} = 4.61$), delayed access to credit information ($\bar{x} = 4.53$), insufficient collateral ($\bar{x} = 4.50$), and the absence of designated bank accounts ($\bar{x} = 4.24$). Other significant barriers were limited farmland ($\bar{x} = 4.12$), high input costs ($\bar{x} = 4.10$), poor road infrastructure ($\bar{x} = 3.99$), bureaucratic loan procedures ($\bar{x} = 3.98$), low financial literacy ($\bar{x} = 3.96$), and high interest rates ($\bar{x} = 3.91$). Additional

issues such as inadequate loan amounts ($\bar{x} = 3.85$), lack of guarantors ($\bar{x} = 3.64$), and small loan sizes ($\bar{x} = 3.01$) were also reported. These constraints collectively reduce farmers' ability to access and effectively utilize formal financial services, thereby limiting agricultural productivity and rural development. Delays in credit disbursement often cause farmers to miss critical planting periods, leading to lower yields and reduced income, as also reported by Nkwi et al. (2022). Similarly, delayed access to credit information restricts timely loan applications (Idris, 2010), while insufficient collateral remains a persistent barrier to credit access among smallholders (Michael et al., 2018). The absence of formal bank accounts and inadequate farmland further restrict farmers' eligibility for loans (Idris, 2010; Yahaya et al., 2018). High input costs and poor rural infrastructure continue to weaken farmers' financial capacity and limit market access (Nwosu et al., 2017; Yahaya et al., 2018). Bureaucratic bottlenecks in loan processing discourage participation in formal financial systems (Nkwi et al., 2022), while low financial literacy contributes to poor understanding of loan conditions and mismanagement of credit (Michael et al., 2018). High interest rates also deter borrowing, reinforcing dependence on informal credit sources (Ajah et al., 2017). Moreover, inadequate loan amounts and lack of guarantors further constrain productive investment and credit access (Akinbode, 2013; Ajah et al., 2017).

Table 6: Constraints to Utilization of Formal Financial Services by the Respondents

Constraints	Mean
Untimely disbursement of credit	4.61*
Untimely credit information	4.53*
Inadequate collateral	4.50*
Lack of specified bank account	4.24*
Lack of large farm land	4.12*
High cost of inputs (fertilizer among other farm inputs)	4.10*
Poor roads	3.99*
Bureaucratic hurdles in accessing institutional financial services	3.98*
Limited financial literacy	3.96*
High interest rate	3.91*
Inadequate amount of loan given	3.85*
Lack of guarantor	3.64*
Low volume of credit	3.01*
Poor sales of product	2.50
Climate change effects on rice production	2.46
Cultural barrier	2.27
Theft of rice on the field	2.19
Inadequate processing facilities	2.12
Lack of farm recoding keeping	1.54
Risk of natural disasters in rice production	1.50
Limited access to market	1.38
Rice farming is a seasonal source of income	1.30
Inadequate infrastructural facilities in rural areas	0.79

Decision rule = A weighted mean of ≥ 3.0 will mean serious constraint, while any weighted mean of < 3.0 will mean not a serious constraint

** = Serious constraint

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that institutional financial services are widely available to rice farmers in Nasarawa State, primarily through cooperative societies, NGOs, and commercial banks. However, their utilization has not translated into significant improvements in household livelihood status. This weak relationship is likely due to factors such as inadequate collateral, delays in credit disbursement, high interest rates,

limited financial literacy, and bureaucratic loan processes. Although most farmers are aware of and engage with formal financial institutions, the benefits are not fully realized because loans are often small, delayed, or diverted from productive uses. Furthermore, infrastructural challenges such as poor roads and inadequate access to markets continue to constrain the effective use of institutional finance. Therefore, improving the timeliness and accessibility of financial services, simplifying loan procedures, and integrating livelihood-supporting programs could enhance the contribution of financial institutions to rural development. The study recommends that financial institutions should ensure timely loan disbursement during key production periods and adopt collateral substitution mechanisms such as group lending and cooperative guarantees to ease credit access. Policies should be implemented to reduce interest rates on agricultural loans and align them with farming cycles. Additionally, investments in rural infrastructure, including roads and market facilities, are essential to improve access to financial institutions and markets.

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